

MODERN PROBLEMS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AT THE UNIVERSITY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8146019>

Abstract. *The article describes the ways of mastering physical training by the younger generation, their influence both on life in general and separately on physical and mental components. Methods and recommendations for improving physical education among young people are indicated.*

Keywords: *study, physical education, physical activity, psychology, sports psychology, personal approach, individual characteristics.*

INTRODUCTION

Studies conducted over the past years, more and more often give results that indicate a deterioration in the state of health of students and a decrease in their physical fitness. Thus, the classical models of physical education become ineffective in the modern socio-cultural situation. To increase the effectiveness of the educational process, the introduction of new organizational, methodological and psychological ideas is required, and the search for new approaches to physical education is no less important. Thus, the relevance of this work lies in the study of not only methodological, but also psychological and pedagogical aspects of physical culture and sports, which directly affect the development of physical education of students. [1]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Physical education is a system of socio-pedagogical activities aimed at improving health, the formation of vital motor skills and abilities, as well as the harmonious development of human functions and capabilities. Physical education is a means of forming a comprehensively developed personality, optimizing the physiological and physical condition of students in the learning process.

Physical education is one of the important aspects of physical education taught in all educational institutions. Physical education is designed to develop physical fitness, motor skills, as well as knowledge and skills of a healthy lifestyle, intelligence and the development of self-discipline, it is a way of developing physical exercises necessary for a fulfilling life. [2]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The processes of physical and psychological education have a significant impact on a person, his inner world and behavior. So, with the influence of physical exercises on a person, the nature of the activity of body systems and organs changes, resistance to diseases increases, to the action of irritating factors on the body, thereby strengthening mental and somatic health. It is important that physical exercises have a positive effect on the mental development of students, and that the students themselves receive basic knowledge about the mechanisms of the impact of sports on the body as a whole.

Mastering professional knowledge by a student in the context of a constant increase in the volume of information requires him to rationally manage his free time to relieve mental fatigue and improve health in general. Thus, the full development of the curriculum of the university seems

difficult without physical education, which increases the overall performance. It can be noted that physical education acts as a serious factor that optimizes the mental activity of students. [3]

As for the tasks of physical education, they are:

- education of universal human values;
- preservation and strengthening of the student's health (the base necessary to maintain mental performance throughout the entire period of study and subsequent work activity);
- formation of a habit and sustainable interest in regular physical exercises (the development of the positive impact of physical exercises occurs with systematic sports);
- achievements of general physical fitness (in accordance with the volume of requirements and norms of the university program);
- providing professional-applied physical training (taking into account the nature and characteristics of future labor activity);
- formation and development of leadership skills, inclusion in active sports activities;
- education of hygienic skills, acquisition of knowledge in the field of physical exercises and hardening.

Physical education of students in higher educational institutions is carried out throughout the entire period of student education. The main form of their conduct is training sessions. They are planned in the curricula for all specialties, and their implementation is provided by teachers of physical culture departments throughout the entire time of students' education. Thus, the material of the curriculum provides for solving the problems of physical education and consists of two sections: theoretical and practical. The practical section, in turn, contains educational material aimed at solving specific problems of physical education of students.

The classes presented in the curriculum may not fully restore the lack of physical activity of students, ensure the restoration of their mental performance, and it is also possible to prevent the development of diseases that develop against the background of chronic fatigue. This problem can be solved by conducting independent physical education classes for 4-6 hours a week by students. They allow students to perform a weekly amount of physical activity, contribute to a better assimilation of educational material on physical education.

Organization of independent work of students in physical culture is an urgent problem. It can be done in the following areas:

- awareness of the need for independent work (conversations, lectures), which will help in the formation of physical culture and a knowledge base for educating its value for future specialists;
- development of methods for self-study (questionnaires and observation, development of the necessary programs for the development of various qualities, taking into account the desire of students to choose various forms of classes).

CONCLUSION

It should also be remembered that in building work on physical culture, which will be based on the goal of achieving the educational effect of students, it is important to remember that it is necessary to take into account and study the individual characteristics of students. Only in this case, the most important pedagogical principle of individual approach can be realized, the importance of which in the choice of means of physical exercises for the formation of mental health is no less than in didactic activity.

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